

Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of some water soluble Zn^{II} azide complexes with (*E*)-N-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)anilines

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Abstract : Four neutral zinc(II) azide complexes of composition [Zn(N₃)₂(Lⁿ)], where Lⁿ = (*E*)-N-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)anilines were synthesized. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Visible, fluorescence, IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Efforts for getting single crystals suitable for X-ray crystal structure could not be achieved. However, from spectroscopic data and on the basis of the structures of the related zinc(II) complexes reported earlier in the literature, the complexes could be proposed to adopt four co-ordinated tetrahedral geometry. The complexes were also screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activities against various bacterial strains and were compared with standard drug. Complexes 1 and 2 were found to exhibit effective antibacterial activity against all the tested bacterial strains.

Keywords : Water soluble zinc(II) azide complexes, (*E*)-N-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)anilines, antibacterial activities.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff base represent a series of compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen ligands donor atoms that have been widely studied^{1,2}. The presence of more electronegative nitrogen, oxygen or sulphur atoms on the ligand structure is established to enhance the antibacterial and antitumor activities^{3,4}. Tridentate Schiff bases NNS donor ligands complexes of Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} were found to active against leukemia⁵. The complexes of NS donor ligands showed good activity against Gram-positive bacteria and yeast⁶. On the other hand, nano-structures of zinc azide complexes showed antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and studied their interaction of the complexes with DNA⁷.

In the present scenario, Schiff base complex formation has been extended in presence of pseudohalides, azide or thiocyanate linker owing to their ambidentate character⁸⁻¹⁰. The azido-bridged

complexes have attracted intense interest due to the coordination versatility of the azido bridge¹¹⁻¹⁴. Besides, azide is also used as a ligand to study the interaction between small molecules and metal centres of metalloenzymes¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Since the azide group is bioactive¹⁸ and the azide ion inhibits photosynthetic phosphorylation¹⁹, phosphate transfer²⁰ and endogenous respiration²¹, the complexes which contain azide as the ligand showed some interesting behaviour. The azide ion, being very reactive, acts as an inhibitor in various biological systems by blocking the substrate binding sites²². On the other hand, in manganese biosystems, the azide ion is known to inhibit the superoxide dismutation in mononuclear superoxide dismutases via binding to the metal at the active site in both the Mn^{II} and Mn^{III} oxidation states²³. Moreover inorganic azides function as enzyme inhibitors, the replacement of the inorganic azide which are toxic by an organic azide could be beneficial²⁴⁻²⁷. The latter are better tolerated under physiological condi-

tions and are relatively inert in the biological medium²⁸.

In this context, the study of the transition metal complexes with Schiff bases and azide anion becomes interesting in view of all the above observations. Thus, in an effort towards the development of metallo drugs as chemotherapeutic agents with interesting biological properties such as antibacterial activity we report herein, the synthesis of four water soluble zinc(II) complexes with ligands (L^{1-4}) (prepared *in situ* derived from thiophene-2-carboxyaldehyde and substituted anilines) viz. (*E*)-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene) aniline, (*E*)-2-methyl-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene) aniline, (*E*)-4-methyl-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene) aniline and (*E*)-4-chloro-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene) aniline. Consequently, the zinc compounds **1-4** were investigated for their antibacterial activity against some bacteria and compared with standard compound, Gentamycin.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Reactions for the formation of the compounds **1-4** were carried out in methanol or ethanol using 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratios. In either solvent, one equivalent of $Zn(N_3)_2$ (generated *in situ* from $Zn(OAc)_2$ and NaN_3) reacts rapidly with one equivalent of L (generated *in situ* from thiophene-2-carboxyaldehyde and substituted anilines) to give a yellow precipitate, from which zinc(II) compounds of general stoichiometry $[Zn(N_3)_2(L^{1-4})]$ were isolated. The complexes have been corroborated by the micro-analytical results, which clearly evidenced the formation of 1 : 1 adducts between the bidentate S, N-donors L^{1-4} and $Zn(N_3)_2$. In all cases, air stable pale yellow solids were obtained in moderate to good yields and these compounds behave as non-electrolytes in acetonitrile solution. The ligand skeleton system used in the synthesis of zinc(II) complexes with (*E*)-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)anilines (L^{1-4}) and the structural motifs of zinc azide complexes are shown in Fig. 1.

Spectroscopic characterization :

IR spectroscopy :

The complexes **1-4** depicted very similar infrared

Fig. 1. Structural motifs of zinc(II) (N_3)₂ complexes with L^{1-4} and generic structure of the ligands abbreviations L^n ($n = 1-4$) with the numbering protocol.

spectrum and the assignments of selected diagnostic bands are given in the Experimental section. The entire complexes spectrum compared with literature value. The complexes display a moderately intense IR band in the region $1590-1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is assigned for $\nu_{\text{asym}}(C(H)=N)$ stretching frequency of the coordinated Schiff base ligands²⁹⁻³¹. In addition, well resolved sharp bands of variable intensity observed in the regions 846, 856-872 and $714-730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to the coordinated sulphur of the thiophene ring³²⁻³⁴. In all the complexes, it is worth mentioning that the very strong IR absorption band at around 2037 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(N_3)$ ^{35,36}, which may be attributed to the presence of non-bridging terminal azide in the Zn^{II} azide complexes.

¹H NMR spectroscopy :

¹H NMR spectra of the complexes **1-4** displayed the expected signals and confirmed the presence of the ligand skeleton in the respective complexes in $CDCl_3$ solution. The detail spectral feature of the complexes is given in the Experimental section. In the spectra, the change of ligands coordination to the Zn^{II} upon the ¹H NMR chemical shifts could not be confined in the absence of the NMR data for the free ligands^{29,30} (prepared *in situ* see Experimental). The ¹H NMR spectra of all the compounds show a singlet peak at around 8.5-8.9 ppm which may be assigned to C(H)=N protons. A singlet peak appeared around 2.3 ppm is due to the methyl group in compounds **2** and **3**. The multiplets observed at around 6.7-8.3 ppm in all the complexes are due to protons of the

aromatic ring^{37,34}.

UV and fluorescence spectroscopy :

The photophysical properties of the complexes **1-4** are summarized in Table 1. The absorption spectra of all complexes were recorded in the range 200–600 nm in acetonitrile solutions at concentrations of $\sim 10^{-5} M$; they generally comprise two bands (Fig. 2a). The electronic spectra exhibits a coalescence absorption at around 280 nm and 320 nm (Fig. 2a). The origin of the band could not be assigned due to the non-availability of data for the free ligands²⁹. The steady-state fluorescence studies have been employed as independent evidence of complexation. In acetonitrile solution, the complexes have emission bands at around $\lambda_{em} = 380$ nm and 405 nm and within the wavelength range of 350–500 nm when they are excited at their respective absorption maxima (Fig. 2b) at room temperature. Nevertheless, these emissions could not be confined as metal-to-ligand charge transfer (MLCT) or ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) as the zinc(II) ion with a d^{10} configuration is not easily oxidized or reduced³⁸. The emissions are suggested to be intra ligand (IL) ($\pi-\pi^*$) emission and the Zn compounds showed very low fluorescence quantum yields^{39,40} (Table 1).

Table 1. Photophysical data for complexes **1-4** in acetonitrile solution

Complexes	Electronic spectroscopic data λ_{max} (nm); ($\epsilon[M^{-1}]$)	Photoluminescence data	
		λ_{em} (nm)	Φ_F
1	280, 312(48416)	373, 406	0.12
2	273, 318(46200)	384, 406	0.18
3	272, 319(14333)	383, 404	0.17
4	273, 319(15166)	368, 405	0.23

Proposed structure of the complexes :

In the coordination chemistry, four coordination number is by far the most common in the chemistry of zinc(II) complexes. The four coordination number is generally observed to be tetrahedral and squareplanar⁴¹ and only a few can be classified as (distorted) squareplanar^{42–47}. However, from the spectroscopic data analysis of the similar ligand system reported earlier³⁷, the ligands are proposed to be

Fig. 2. (a) UV-Vis spectra of compounds **1-4** in acetonitrile solution (concentration $\sim 10^{-5} M$). (b) Fluorescence spectra of compounds **1-4** in acetonitrile solution (concentration $\sim 10^{-5} M$) obtained by excitation at the respective absorption maxima.

bi-dentate nature of coordination. The IR spectra of the complexes indicated that L^{1-4} behaves as a bidentate ligand, coordinated to the metal ions viz. azomethine N, thiophene S^{37,48–50}. However, from

the IR spectrum of the complexes, it is worth mentioning that the very strong band at around 2037 cm^{-1} corresponds to stretching frequency of $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{N}_3)^{35,36}$. From the molar conductance data, it was found that the Zn^{II} chelates may be considered non electrolytes in solution²⁹. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes are in good agreement with the formation of the expected compounds^{50,51}. On the basis of above observations, the complexes thought to be four coordinated geometry around zinc atom. In all the complexes, zinc is coordinated with one nitrogen atom of each azide ion and one nitrogen and one sulphur atom of the ligand and therefore, proposed to have tetrahedral structure of the complexes (Fig. 1). In the complexes, it is assumed that the azide is coordinated to the metal as non-bridging terminal fashion and it is reflected in broad unresolved IR absorption band at around $2037\text{--}2086\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Moreover, the Zn^{II} complexes of various bidentate ligands reported earlier⁵²⁻⁵⁷ also confirmed to be tetrahedral geometry. Furthermore, it is also reported that when zinc is coordinated with N, S donor ligands⁵⁸⁻⁶¹, it shows preferably tetrahedral geometry^{60,62-64}. The proposed tetrahedral structure is based on the IR spectroscopic data of the complexes where each azides are assumed to be present as non-bridging terminal bonding to the metal and it is also supported from the X-ray crystal structure of Zn^{II} non-bridging azide tetrahedral complexes^{65,52}. In con-

clusion, the proposed tetrahedral structure of the Zn^{II} azide complexes are tentative and is difficult to give a conclusive structure without single crystal X-ray structure.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activities of the synthesized compounds **1-4** were screened against two Gram-negative and two Gram-positive bacteria. Four bacterial strains *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* were employed for the antibacterial assay. The results of the screening of the antibacterial activity of the synthesized zinc(II) compounds along with the standard compound, Gentamycin as positive control are listed in Table 2. It can be seen from the table that compound **1** was found to be effective against all the tested bacteria strains while compound **2** showed activity against three bacteria strains *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *B. cereus*. Other compounds showed activity against *E. coli* only. From the table, it has also been observed that, there is a slight increase in the activity of the compounds as concentration per well increase from 100 to 150 μg during the test. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the compounds were also determined and the results are shown in Table 3. MICs of only those compounds which showed activity against the tested bacterial strain were determined. From the table it is clear that compounds **1** and **2** exhibited MICs in the range 12.5-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ against

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds **1-4** (zone of inhibition in mm) at different concentrations (100 and 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$) along with standard compounds

Sl. No.	Tested compounds	Conc. ($\mu\text{g}/\text{Well}$) ^a	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	1	150	10	8	11	15
		100	8	7	10	12
2.	2	150	8	–	10	10
		100	7	–	8	8
3.	3	150	–	–	–	8
		100	–	–	–	7
4.	4	150	12	–	–	–
		100	10	–	–	–
5.	Gentamycin	10	16	20	22	18
6.	DMSO	30 μL	–	–	–	–

For the compounds^a : 30 μL (150 μg) and 20 μL (100 μg) respectively were used per well from the stock solution (5 mg/mL); For the standard antibiotic : 10 μL (10 μg) were used per well was employed from the stock solution (1 mg/mL) : – “not active”; + ve control : Gentamycin for antibacterial; –ve control : DMSO.

Table 3. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) for antibacterial activities of the compounds **1-4** and standard drug (concentration in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)

Compounds	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1	25	50	50	12.5
2	50	50	50	50
3	–	–	–	50
4	50	–	–	–
Gentamycin	5	5	5	5

– : Not applicable.

S. aureus and compound **1** showed higher activity (MIC at 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) against *E. coli* as compared to compound **2**. However, the antibacterial activity of this series were found to be lower than the standard compound Gyntamycin which showed MIC = 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

Caution! While no incident occurred whilst using azide during preparation and isolation, care in handling azides must be exercised owing to their potentially explosive nature.

All chemicals were used as purchased without purification. Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde, aniline, Zn(OAc)₂, NaN₃ (Merck), *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine (CDH), *p*-chloroaniline (Merck). Solvents were purified following standard procedures and were freshly distilled prior to use. The ligands L¹⁻⁴ viz. (*E*)-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)aniline derivatives were prepared *in situ* from thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde and the corresponding anilines. Attempts to prepare crystalline (*E*)-*N*-(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)aniline derivatives were unsuccessful and in all instances either oil or a viscous liquid was isolated. Melting points were recorded in capillary tubes on a Scanca apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} were obtained using KBr pellets on a Shimadzu FT-IR-8400S spectrophotometer and UV-Visible spectra of the complexes were observed in UV-1800 Shimadzu spectrophotometer in ACN at 200–800 nm range. Fluorescence spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrofluorimeter model LS55 (with the excitation and emission slits fixed at 10 and 20 nm, respectively) and corrected for the instrument response

function. Quartz cuvettes of 10 mm optical path length received from Perkin-Elmer, USA (part no. B0831009) and Hellma, Germany (Type 111-QS) were used for measuring absorption and fluorescence spectra, respectively. Fluorescence quantum yields (ϕ_f) were calculated by comparing the total fluorescence intensity over the whole fluorescence spectroscopic range with that of a standard using the method described elsewhere^{66,29,30}. The relative experimental error of the measured ϕ_f was estimated to be within $\pm 10\%$. Solution electrical conductivity measurements were made using a Eutech instruments automatic precision bridge Con510. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II spectrometer and measured at 400.13 MHz. The ¹H chemical shifts were referenced to Me₄Si set at 0.00 ppm.

Synthesis of zinc(II) compounds :

Details of the procedures have been outlined for the synthesis of complex **1**.

Synthesis of [Zn(N₃)₂(L¹)] (**1**) :

Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde (0.50 g, 4.45 mmol) was taken in ethanol (5 mL) and to that added a solution of aniline (0.415 g, 4.45 mmol) in ethanol (10 mL). The mixture was stirred at ambient temperature for 30 min and was added drop-wise to a stirred methanolic solution containing Zn(N₃)₂ (prepared *in situ* from the reaction of Zn(OAc)₂ (0.811 g, 4.42 mmol) in 20 mL methanol with an excess of NaN₃ (0.57 g, 8.84 mmol) in 30 mL methanol), which resulted in the immediate formation of a yellow precipitate. The stirring was continued for 3 h and then the mixture was filtered. The residue was washed thoroughly with water and then with methanol (3 × 5 mL) and dried *in vacuo*. The dried solid was dissolved by boiling in 60 mL of acetonitrile and filtered while hot. The filtrate, upon cooling to room temperature, afforded a yellow crystalline material. Yield 0.90 g (40%), m.p. 152–153 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₁H₉N₇SZn : C, 39.24; H, 2.69; N, 29.12. Found : C, 40.30; H, 3.00; N, 30.66%. Λ_m (CH₃CN) : 9 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$. 1600 ν_{asym} (C(H)=N); 824 ν_{asym} (C-S-C) thiophene; 2037 ν_{asym} (N₃). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.56 (1H, s, H-7), 7.86 (1H, d, H-3'), 7.82 (1H, d, H-5'), 7.40 (1H, t, H-4'), 7.38 (1H, d, H-2), 7.34

(1H, d, H-6), 7.22 (1H, t, H-3) 7.20 (1H, t, H-5), 7.08 (1H, t, H-4) ppm. Complexes **2-4** were prepared as yellow crystalline compound in a manner similar to that described for the preparation of **1** using appropriate anilines and metal salts as starting materials.

Synthesis of [Zn(N₃)₂(L²)] (2) :

Yield 0.85 g (36%), m.p. 84–85 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁N₇SZn : C, 41.10; H, 3.16; N, 27.96. Found : C, 42.30; H, 3.60; N, 28.66%. Λ_m (CH₃CN) : 2 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1616 ν_{asym} (C(H)=N) imine; 842 ν_{asym} (C-S-C) thiophene; 2037 ν_{asym} (N₃). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : 8.46 (1H, s, H-7), 7.50 (1H, d, H-3'), 7.46 (1H, d, H-5'), 7.21 (1H, t, H-4'), 7.17 (1H, d, H-3), 7.11 (2H, m, H-4,5), 6.93 (1H, d, H-6), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of [Zn(N₃)₂(L³)] (3) :

Yield 0.91 g (37%), m.p. 74–75 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁N₇SZn : C, 41.10; H, 3.16; N, 27.96. Found : C, 39.70; H, 3.90; N, 27.66%. Λ_m (CH₃CN) : 2 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1615 ν_{asym} (C(H)=N) imine; 819 ν_{asym} (C-S-C) thiophene; 2052 ν_{asym} (N₃). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : 8.57 (1H, s, H-7), 7.49 (1H, d, H-3'), 7.46 (1H, d, H-5'), 7.19 (1H, t, H-4'), 7.14 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.12 (2H, d, H-2,6), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of [Zn(N₃)₂(L⁴)] (4) :

Yield 0.75 g (31%), m.p. 94–95 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₁H₈ClN₇SZn : C, 35.60; H, 2.17; N, 26.42. Found : C, 36.00; H, 3.00; N, 29.00%. Λ_m (CH₃CN) : 6 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1614 ν_{asym} (C(H)=N) imine; 840 ν_{asym} (C-S-C) thiophene; 2086 ν_{asym} (N₃). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : 8.54 (1H, s, H-7), 7.53 (1H, d, H-3'), 7.51 (1H, d, H-5'), 7.32 (1H, t, H-4'), 7.16 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.14 (2H, d, H-2,6).

Antibacterial assay :

Four bacteria strain *Escherichia coli* (ATCC-11229), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC-15442), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-11632) and *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC-430), were used for the antibacterial assay. The microbial growth inhibitory potential of the compounds was determined using the Agar Well diffusion method⁶⁷ with some modification as reported

earlier⁶⁴. Sterile Petri plates (90 mm) were prepared with 20–25 mL of sterile Luria Bertani Agar (LBA) (Himedia) and allowed to solidify. 100 μ L of adjusted test cultures (10⁸ CFU/mL) swabbed on the top of the solidified media and allowed to dry for 10 min on the plates. Solidified plates were punched to make well of 6 mm diameter with the help of sterile coke borer. Next, 50 μ L and 30 μ L of each compounds dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; 5 mg/mL) was added into the well. Gentamycin (10 μ g/well) (stock-1 mg/mL) in sterile distilled water was used as positive control for the bacteria and a well containing only DMSO (30 μ L) was used as a negative control. Culture plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. At the end of the incubation, the diameter of the inhibition zones formed around the wells was measured in millimetre. All tests were performed triplicate. The MICs of the compounds and reference compound were determined as reported⁶⁸. The test sample was first dissolved in 10% (v/v) DMSO/MHB to give a final concentration 500 μ g/mL. This was serially diluted two fold to obtain concentration ranges of 0.425–50 μ g/mL and standard was found in the concentration range of 0.156–10 μ g/mL. Then 100 μ L of each concentration was added in a well (96-well micro plate) containing 100 μ L of inoculum. An inoculum density of 1 \times 10⁶ CFU/mL of bacterial strains was prepared in normal saline (9 g/L) by comparison with a 0.5 MacFarland turbidity standard with appropriate dilution⁶⁹. The negative control well consisted of 100 μ L of MHB and 100 μ L of the standard inoculum only⁷⁰. The plates were covered and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The assay was repeated three times. The MICs of sample was detected following addition (40 μ L) of 0.2 mg/mL Nitroblue Tetrazolium chloride (NBT) (Himedia) to microplates wells and incubated at 37 °C for 30 min following the reported procedure⁷¹. Viable microorganisms reduced the yellow to black and MIC was defined as the lowest sample concentration of drug at which there was no visible growth of the organism.

Conclusions

The syntheses of four neutral water soluble zinc(II)azide complexes with substituted (*E*)-N-

(thiophen-2-ylmethylene)anilines were successfully accomplished. These compounds have been characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, UV-Visible and fluorescence spectroscopy. In all the cases, the compounds behave as non-electrolytes in acetonitrile solution. UV-Visible, fluorescence and IR spectral study indicate that the ligands (L¹⁻⁴) are coordinated to the metal complexes. The emission spectra of all the complexes shows π-π* (*intra-ligand*) transition. The study of the complexes suggested to be four coordinated tetrahedral geometry around zinc atom. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was investigated against some bacteria and complexes **1** and **2** were found to exhibit effective activity. However, the complexes were found to be lower activity than the standard compound.

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